

3-SHO'BA

SUN'IY INTELLEKT

THE MATHEMATICAL ESSENCE OF LOGISTIC REGRESSION FOR MACHINE LEARNING

DSc, prof. Rahimov Nodir

Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, r_nodir@mail.ru

associate prof. Khasanov Dilmurod

Tashkent university of information technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, tatusf2015@gmail.com

Annotation: this article inform about mathematical aspect of Logistic Regression algorithm. Logistic Regression algorithm is one of the most popular algorithm among Regression algorithms. As well as, you can find advantages and disadvantages Logistic Regression algorithm.

Keywords: logistic regression equation, cost function, linear regression, sigmoid function, mean squared error.

Logistic regression is one of the most popular Machine Learning algorithms, which comes under the Supervised Learning technique. It is used for predicting the categorical dependent variable using a given set of independent variables. This algorithm predicts the output of a categorical dependent variable. Therefore, the outcome must be a categorical or discrete value. It can be either Yes or No, 0 or 1, true or False, etc. but instead of giving the exact value as 0 and 1, it gives the probabilistic values which lie between 0 and 1 [2].

Logistic Regression is much similar to the Linear Regression except that how they are used. Linear Regression is used for solving Regression problems, whereas Logistic regression is used for solving the classification problems. In Logistic regression, instead of fitting a regression line, we fit an "S" shaped logistic function, which predicts two maximum values (0 or 1). Logistic regression has become particularly popular in online advertising, enabling marketers to predict the likelihood of specific website users who will click on particular advertisements as a yes or no

percentage. The curve from the logistic function indicates the likelihood of something such as whether the cells are cancerous or not, a mouse is obese or not based on its weight, etc. To find the math behind this, I plunged deeper into this topic only to find myself a better understanding of the Logistic Regression model. And in this article, you can see answers all the doubts you are having right now on this topic. I will tell you the math behind this regression model.

First of all, we will see the graph of Logistic Regression. This is a significant machine learning algorithm because it has the ability to provide probabilities and classify new data using continuous and discrete datasets. Logistic Regression can be used to classify the observations using different types of data and can easily determine the most effective variables used for the classification. The below image is showing the logistic function:

Figure 1. Logistic (Sigmoid) Line with data values in 2D coordinate system.

The sigmoid function is a mathematical function used to map the predicted values to probabilities. It maps any real value into another value within a range of 0 and 1. The value of the logistic regression must be between 0 and 1, which cannot go beyond this limit, so it forms a curve like the "S" form. The S-form curve is called the Sigmoid function or the logistic function.

In logistic regression, we use the concept of the threshold value, which defines the probability of either 0 or 1. Such as values above the threshold value tends to 1, and a value below the threshold values tends to 0 [2].

Advantages and disadvantages of logistic regression. The main advantage of logistic regression is that it is much easier to set up and train than other machine learning and AI applications. Another advantage is that it is one of the most efficient algorithms when the different outcomes or distinctions represented by the data are

linearly separable. This means that you can draw a straight line separating the results of a logistic regression calculation [3].

One of the biggest attractions of logistic regression for statisticians is that it can help reveal the interrelationships between different variables and their impact on outcomes. This could quickly determine when two variables are positively or negatively correlated, such as the finding cited above that more studying tends to be correlated with higher test outcomes. But it is important to note that other techniques like causal AI are required to make the leap from correlation to causation.

Logistic Regression Equation:

$$P = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)}}$$

the equation of the best fit line in linear regression is:

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x$$

instead of y we are taking probabilities (P). But there is an issue here, the value of (P) will exceed 1 or go below 0 and we know that range of Probability is (0-1)[6].

To overcome this issue we take “odds” of P :

$$P = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x$$

$$\frac{P}{1 - P} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x$$

By restricting the range we are actually decreasing the number of data points and of course, if we decrease our data points, our correlation will decrease. It is difficult to model a variable that has a restricted range. To control this we take the *log of odds* which has a range from $(-\infty, +\infty)$ [3].

$$\log\left(\frac{P}{1 - P}\right) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x$$

To do so we will multiply by *exponent* on both sides and then solve for P .

$$p = p\left[\frac{e^{(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)}}{p} - e^{(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)}\right]$$

$$1 = \frac{e^{(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)}}{p} - e^{(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)}$$

$$p = \frac{e^{(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)}}{1 + e^{(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)}} \quad \longrightarrow \quad p = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-(\beta_0 + \beta_1 x)}}$$

Mean Squared Error (MSE) function is used as cost function for this algorithm.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_{i=1}^m (f(x_i) - y_i)^2 \quad [9].$$

In conclusion, in this article we have learned why linear regression does not work for classification problems. Also how MLE is used in logistic regression and how our cost function is obtained.

References

1. Daniel Nelson. What is Gradient Descent. (internet source). 2020.
2. Javatpoint.com tutorial website for Data Science beginners. “Logistic Regression in Machine Learning”.
3. Anshul Saini, “Conceptual Understanding of Logistic Regression Data science beginners”(web-article), analyticsvidhya.com.
4. Oliver Theobald. Machine Learning for Absolute Beginners. – Scatterplot Press. 2017. pg.43-98
5. N.Raximov, O.Primqulov, B.Daminova,“[Basic concepts and stages of research development on artificial intelligence](#)”, International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies (ICISCT), www.ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9670085/metrics#metrics
6. N.Rahimov, D.Khasanov,J.Kuvandikov, “Structural-funtional organization correctness of knowledge models of product systems”, Harvard educational and scientific review, Vol.2. Issue 2 Pg. 1-9.
7. Khasanov Dilmurod, [Tojiyev Ma’ruf](#),Primqulov Oybek., “Gradient Descent In Machine”. International Conference on Information Science and Communications Technologies(ICISCT), <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9670169Babomurodov>
8. O. Zh., Rakhimov N. O. Stages of knowledge extraction from electronic information resources. Eurasian Union of Scientists. International Popular Science Bulletin. Issue. № 10(19)/2015. – pp. 130-133. ISSN: 2411-6467
9. N.Rahimov, D.Khasanov,“The application of multiple linear regression algorithm and python for crop yield prediction in agriculture”, Harvard educational and scientific review, Vol.2. Issue 1 Pg. 181-187.